

A CASE STUDY OF TOURISM-RELATED CONFLICT IN PARASNATH, JHARKHAND

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Abstract

Land is restricted, rare and valuable. It stands for territoriality or the scope of a person's authority. The reason for the conflict is the land dispute between neighbouring states and between people. The Parasnath. The hills are located in the Indian state of Jharkhand's Giridih district. One of the holiest places for the Jain people to visit is the hills, where they have constructed temples and tonks. There is fauna on the hills. Sanctuaries, and a plan for tourism development was being worked on. The Jain community objected to the change, citing their religious concerns as justification. The Jain sect abstains from alcohol and only eats vegetarianism. In the meantime, the Adivasis, an Aboriginal group, also made claims to the Parasnath hills. This essay investigates the triangle dispute in the hills of Parasnath and offers suggestions for how to resolve disputes.

1. Introduction

A location becomes sacred when there is an emotional bond, sacralisation, and sense of devotion to it. It might be a house of worship or a place of residence (Das *et al.*, 2023). Sacred sites are frequently connected to intense religious zeal. For adherents of a certain faith, birthplaces, places of attainment, and locations associated with death are sacred. When two faiths collide at one place in a space frame, conflict results. The superiority and dominance are frequently seen in multiple places. Examples of conflicts at places of worship include Jerusalem, the Hagia Sophia in Turkey, Ayodhya in India, and most recently, Parasnath in Jharkhand, Australia.

While some studies suggest that religion helps with peace building, healing, and reconciliation, others contend that religion increases conflict, fuels animosity, and encourages retaliation (Lundy *et al.*, 2018). When people think they are distinct from other people and their religious allegiance prevents them from enduring for tolerance, conflict arises (Asmara & Noho, 2022).

Religious tolerance is at an all-time low in every community, despite the fact that all religions preach harmony and peace. Under the pretext of protecting religion, militancy and tragic bloodshed have crept into every faith (Oko, 2021).

In Jharkhand, India's Giridih district is home to the Parasnath Hills. These hills are located on the Chhota Nagpur plateau's Eastern Section. The relief around the Parasnath hills varies more than in the other regions. These hills are home to a few Jain temples as well as several Tonks devoted to Tirthankaras. Tonks are little buildings in the Jain religion that are connected to Tirthankaras who received moksha, or salvation, there. For Jains, it is one of the most sacred sites. On these Parasnath hills, it is thought that 20 of the 26 Tirthankaras (Jain monks) achieved Moksha (salvation) (Amarnath Tewary, 2023). There are numerous indigenous villages encircling these hills.

Figure 1 Location of Tonks, Temple and Jal Mandir on Parasnath Hills, Giridih, Jharkhand Source: shikharji.org

A wildlife sanctuary covering 49.33 square kilometers and made up of mixed deciduous woodland is located in the hills. In August 2019, the Central Government declared Parasnath Hills to be an environmentally sensitive area. This granted the State Government the authority to create a plan for tourism development.

The State Government of the goal of Jharkhand was to become a center for religious tourism. The Jain community in India condemned the move. The state government instructed the authorities not to sell alcohol or non-vegetarian food near the Parasnath hills in order to preserve the site's holiness as a Jain religious site. Jain communities have very particular dietary and lifestyle preferences.

The Jains

With Lord Mahavira as the 24th Tirthankara and Lord Rishabh as the first, Jainism is one of the oldest religions in India. The Jain holy sites of Vaishali, Pawapuri, Mount Abu, Parasnath in Jharkhand, and the Ellora Caves are among others. The entire area on and surrounding the Parasnath hills, home to several tonks, temples, and Jal Mandirs, is known as Sammed Shikharjee. The Jain temple known as "Parsvanatha Temple" is located atop the highest point of the Parasnath Hills (1365 m). Similar to Buddhist buildings, Jain constructions are not mysterious. It does not declare that it is closer to God (Kumar & Das, 2018). The following is a list of the nine facts that comprise Jainism's religious rationale.

- i. Soul (jiva)
- ii. Non-Soul (ajiva)
- iii. Legitimate (punya)
- iv. Sin
- v. Surge of karma
- vi. Stoppage of Karmic Matter
- vii. Oppression
- viii. Shedding of Karmic Matter
- ix. Moksha (opportunity)

Jain temples are frequently found atop hills. The Jal Mandir is a feature common to many Jain temples. A trail leads to the temple, which is situated in the middle of the body of water.

One such instance is the Jain temple in Pawapuri. Jains are a peaceful, business-oriented community primarily found in Gujarat and Rajasthan. Temples are composed of white marble stone with elaborate decorations.

Figure 2 Location of Tonks, Temple and Jal Mandir on Parasnath Hills, Giridih, Jharkhand Source: shikharji.org

The Adivasis

The native Indian communities in India are known as Adivasis. They follow customs that are unique to their culture. Jharkhand and Chhattisgarh states were divided as a result of the Adivasi community's popular aspirations. The Parasnath hills are regarded by the Santhals of Jharkhand as Marang Buru, or hill deity. They contend that the Jains

forcibly took control of the Parasnath hills and built temples and tonsks there. These days the Adivasi community and the Jains are at odds over who has ownership of the hills.

Built Environment on Parasnath Hills

The natural environment is not greatly disturbed. Concrete paths designed for trekking measure four to five feet in width and may include stairs. There is a motorized path that leads to a heli-pad located close to Shikharjee. Temporary food stands are constructed in a vernacular style using only natural materials. There are a few hamlets on the hills. For sustainable development, the built environment needs to adapt to the surrounding environment (Nijas *et al.*, 2023). The pinnacle of the natural constructed environment is Parasnath Hill. The permanent constructions are Tonks, temples, and restroom buildings. The following is a list of some of the buildings that have been built on the Parasnath hills.

- i. Temples- Chandranan Prabhu, Jal Mandir, Sri Parsvnath Prabhu,
- ii. Tonks- a small structures
- iii. Barracks- CRPF for security
- iv. Telecom Tower- near main Temple of Parsvnath Prabhu
- v. Helipad
- vi. Toilet Block- on trekking rout

Along the trekking trail are a number of temporary stores selling products in a vernacular construction. In addition to other edibles, they sell tea, pakoras, maggi, sugarcane juices, chips, and biscuits. The Parasnath hills' hill landscape is very tastefully blended with vernacular architecture, resulting in a symbiotic relationship between the built and natural environments (Srivastava & Das, 2023). These sustainable constructed forms have walls made of single-use plastic and beverage water bottles that have a high thermal resistivity, keeping the constructions cool during the summer (Srivastav, 2023). Recently, for the benefit of the birds and other wildlife on the hills, all of the electric light poles were taken down from the woodland walking route. During the night, trekkers use cell phone lighting and torches.

Conflict between Religious tourism and Adventure Tourism

Religious Tourism

In India, religious tourism has existed for a very long time. There are 52 Shaktipeeths, 12 Jyotirlingas, and 4 Dhams spread around the nation according to Hinduism. The Himalayas are home to the locations of Kailash Manasarovar (now in Tibet-controlled China), Kedarnath, Badrinath, Gangotri, Yamunotri, Amarnath, and Mata Vaishno Devi. They've been labeled as adventure tourism recently.

Because these locations are prone to landslides and flash floods, this has been done to guarantee that agencies are prepared for the calamity. The catastrophic cloudburst that occurred in Kedarnath on June 16 and 17, 2013, caused immense damage and resulted in 5748 official deaths. The State Government has imposed a daily cap on the number of tourists that can visit, as indicated in the table below.

Table 1 Limits on no. of Tourist visiting per day.

S. No.	Religious Place	No. of visitors allowed per day
1	Kedarnath	12,000
2	Badrinath	15,000
3	Yamunotri	4,000
4	Gangotri	7,000

Resource : sacredyatra.com

Effect of Disaster on tourist flow at Kedarnath

Figure 3 Effect of Disaster on tourist flow at Kedarnath

There are five most sacred Jain sites in India where the Jain community go for pilgrimage. They are listed below.

- i. Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar
- ii. Shikharjee, Parasnath, Giridih, Jharkhand
- iii. Palitana temples, Shatrunjay hills in Kathiawar, Gujarat
- iv. Girnar Temples, Junagadh, Gujarat
- v. Dilwara temples, Mount Abu, Rajasthan

In addition, there are a number of additional Jain pilgrimage sites, including Ranakpur Temple in Pali district of Rajasthan, Khandgiri, Udaigiri in Orissa, Nathnagar in Bhagalpur, in the state of Bihar, and the Shantinath temple complex in Deogarh.

Adventure Tourism

Adventures on hills include ropeways, bungee jumping hill climbing, trekking, and bicycling. (Choudhury *et al.*, 2023) sports. Tourists are drawn to these adventure activities, and they stay longer at tourist attractions. Due to Parasnath's religious background, these kinds of actions are discouraged by groups of Jain people. Even though there is currently just one route—the trekking route—tourists are still utilizing motorcycles to get to Shikharjee. The trekking trail and palanquins are the only ways to get to the other locations. The highlands of Parasnath provide a great deal of promise, from serenity, divine quiet, and common enjoyment. However, another factor is that the Jain community's religious beliefs will be undermined by the growth of Parasnath Hills as a tourist destination. An alternative route could be the 54-kilometer parikrama of the entire Parasnath highlands at Tahalti (Hill Base) (Kumar *et al.*, 2017). Given the region's (Jharkhand's) great diversity in terms of hills, dams, waterfalls, national parks, wildlife sanctuaries, and religious ties, sustainable tourism could boost the state's economy (Prasad, 2008). In a place with abundant forest diversity, ecotourism may offer an alternative means of drawing in nature enthusiasts (Saw, 2018).

Figure 4 Lush Green Hills of Parasnath

Conflict Resolution

A religious community and an ethnic community are at odds in Parasnath. The two villages get along well with one another. It's interesting to note that the three stakeholders shown in this image are the Jharkhand forest department, the Adivasi community, and the Jain community. The forest department will be crucial in resolving disputes by serving as a liaison between the local population and protecting the area's ecosystem. A joint committee for the establishment of peace may be formed, along with restrictions on the built environment on the hills, abstinence from alcohol, and non-vegetarianism in the Parasnath region, including the Tehalti at Madhuban. It is not advisable to use Parasnath Hills for adventure and sports tourism. It ought to be limited to spiritual travel.

4. Conclusion

The trait of Indian culture that was diverted by the advent of the West from Persia is harmonic coexistence. Respect and religious tolerance are essential for establishing peace between people of similar faiths. Places of worship shouldn't be combined with adventure travel, and certain licenses may be set aside for environmentally conscious travel that respects mainstream religion. Adivasis should be proud of the hills that give rise to temples and tonsks, and they should see Jain as their own brothers and sisters who share the same ancestry.

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